

Overall study design

Title of the study	Lipid profiling of liver tissue isolated from Cox14 KO mice vs WT control.		
Document creation date	03/28/2024	Corresponding Email	britta.bruegger@bzh.uni-heidelberg.de
Principle investigator	Britta Brügger / Heidelberg Lipidomics Platform	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	Heidelberg University Biochemistry Center	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	Hydrochloric acid		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
MS type	QTrap	Resolution at MS2	Unit
MS vendor	SCIEX	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Profile mode
Direct type	Chip	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	No	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	mtbls9823	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

WT isolated liver tissue flash frozen in liquid nitrogen / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage time (month)	0.5	Sample homogenization solvent	Methanol
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

COX14 isolated liver tissue flash frozen in liquid nitrogen / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage time (month)	0.5	Sample homogenization solvent	Methanol
Freeze-thaw cycles	2		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name	HG(PC,184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

1) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 14:1/14:1	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 20:1/20:1	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 22:1/22:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	Includes PC species with one uneven FA chain
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

2) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 14:1/14:1	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 20:1/20:1	
PC	HG(PC,184)	PC 22:1/22:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPC	HG(PC,184)	LPC 17:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

4) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

4) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SM	HG(PC,184)	SM 31:1;2	
SM	HG(PC,184)	SM 35:1;2	
SM	HG(PC,184)	SM 43:1;2	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	Internal standards semi-synthesized (Özbalci et al., 2013)
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list		
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No		
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No		
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-		
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)		
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction		
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>-HG(PE,141)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Fragment name					
-HG(PE,141)					
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No		
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-		
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes				

5) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No												
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No												
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PE</td> <td>-HG(PE,141)</td> <td>PE 14:1/14:1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PE</td> <td>-HG(PE,141)</td> <td>PE 20:1/20:1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PE</td> <td>-HG(PE,141)</td> <td>PE 22:1/22:1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 14:1/14:1	PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 20:1/20:1	PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 22:1/22:1		
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass													
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 14:1/14:1													
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 20:1/20:1													
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 22:1/22:1													
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No												
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	Internal standards semi-synthesized (Özbalci et al., 2013)												
Type I isotope correction	Yes														

6) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name -HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	Includes PE species with one uneven FA chain
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

6) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 14:1/14:1	
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 20:1/20:1	
PE	-HG(PE,141)	PE 22:1/22:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

7) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name -HG(PS,185)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

7) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PS	-HG(PS,185)	PS 14:1/14:1	
PS	-HG(PS,185)	PS 20:1/20:1	
PS	-HG(PS,185)	PS 22:1/22:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	Internal standards semi-synthesized (Özbalci et al., 2013)
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

8) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-HG(PI,NH3,277)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

8) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PI	-HG(PI,NH3,277)	PS 17:0/20:4	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

9) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list		
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No		
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No		
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-		
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)		
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction		
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>-HG(PG,NH3,189)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Fragment name	-HG(PG,NH3,189)		
Fragment name					
-HG(PG,NH3,189)					
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No		
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	Does not distinguish between PG and LBPA species.		
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes				

9) PG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No												
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No												
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Fragment(s)</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PG</td> <td>-HG(PG,NH3,189)</td> <td>PG 14:1/14:1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PG</td> <td>-HG(PG,NH3,189)</td> <td>PG 20:1/20:1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PG</td> <td>-HG(PG,NH3,189)</td> <td>PG 22:1/22:1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 14:1/14:1	PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 20:1/20:1	PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 22:1/22:1		
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass													
PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 14:1/14:1													
PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 20:1/20:1													
PG	-HG(PG,NH3,189)	PG 22:1/22:1													
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No												
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	Internal standards semi-synthesized (Özbalci et al., 2013)												
Type I isotope correction	Yes														

10) PA[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name -(HG,H3PO4,NH3,115)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

10) PA[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard Fragment(s) Endogenous subclass			
PA	- (HG,H3PO4,NH3,11	PA 17:0/20:4	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name LCB(-H3O2)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

11) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cer	LCB(-H3O2)	Cer(18:1;O2/18:0[D3])	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

12) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name			
LCB(-CH3O2)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

12) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
HexCer	LCB(-H3O2)	Hex-Cer(18:1;O2/17:0)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

13) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name -HG(Hex2,342)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

13) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard Fragment(s) Endogenous subclass			
Hex2Cer	-HG(Hex2,342)	Lac-Cer(18:1;O2/17:0)	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

14) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name -FA1(+HO)-Cholesterol(369)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

14) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
CE	-FA1(+HO)- Cholesterol(369)	CE 9:0	
CE	-FA1(+HO)- Cholesterol(369)	CE 19:0	
CE	-FA1(+HO)- Cholesterol(369)	CE 24:1	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

15) PE P[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-FA2+(C3H5O2)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

15) PE P[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-16:0/15:0[D3]	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-16:0/19:0	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-18:0/15:0[D3]	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-18:0/19:0	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-18:1/15:0[D3]	
PE P	-FA2+(C3H5O2)	PE P-18:1/19:0	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

16) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	Limit of detection	No
Identification level	Species level	Additional dimension/techniques	Derivatization of free cholesterol to cholesteroyl acetate
Polarity mode	Positive	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	High throughput quantification of free cholesterol; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbaliip.2005.12.007
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	No
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Fragment name			
	-NH4C2H3O2(77)		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	Background subtraction
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Which assumptions were presumed?	Analysis with LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta) using a target list		

16) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView (SCIEX, 1.3 beta)
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cholesterol[D7]	-NH4C2H3O2(77)	ST 27:1;O[D7]	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		